

A STUDY ON POSITIVE ASPECTS OF RURAL DEVELOPMENT TRAINING IN KANNUR DISTRICT OF KERALA

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ABSTRACT

As per the scheduled programmes under Ministry of Rural development and Ministry of Drinking Water and sanitation , Government of India , various rural development programmes are being conducted all over India since long. In Kannur district too, various rural development programmes are implemented with due modifications as per the specific social, cultural, geographical and demographical needs as specified my Commissionerate of Rural Development, Kerala. In order to achieve the success of these rural development programmes, frequent training programmes are organized at the three tier levels of Elected Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) namely District Panchayat, Block Panchayats and Gram Panchayats to the stake holders namely Government officials and Elected Panchayati Raj Institution (PRI) Members. Five prominent rural development programmes namely Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA). Indira Awaas Yojana (IAY). Integrated Watershed Management Programme (IWMP), Total Sanitation Campaign (TSC) and PradhanMantriGramin Sadak Yojana (PMGSY) are subjected to this study.

The present study is aimed to assess the Positive Aspects of Rural Development Training imparted to Elected Panchayati Raj Institution (PRI) Members, in Kannur District of Kerala. Samples have been taken on cent per cent level from elected members of Panchayati Raj Institutions in Kannur District Panchayat, 11 Block Panchayats and Presidents and Vice Presidents of Gram Panchayat of 81 gram Panchayats. Positive aspects of the training is assessed based on the responses on Likert scale on questionnaire framed on ten positive aspect criteria. The result of the study indicates that in Kannur district, training in TSC followed by PMGSY has highest responses with positive aspects in training, while MGNREGA had shown very lowest responses. This indicates that MGNREGA training has to take into account the Criteria with positive aspects essentially.

Key Words: Rural Development, Rural Development Programmes, Panchayati Raj Institutions, Positive aspect

INTRODUCTION

In order to improve the sustained livelihood of the people living in rural areas, throughout the world there exists a dedicated effort. According to **Harriss (1982)**, as rural population all over the world is 47 percent of world population and 70 percent of world's poor live rural areas, rural development is an ongoing process all over the world. **Olinto et al (2013)** stated that Rural Development are the initiatives mainly meant for developing economies in underdeveloped countries. Rural Development is meant for overall development of rural areas and thereby it improves the quality of life of rural population (**Sundaram, 2011**). India is the second biggest country in the world where it's seventy percent population living in rural areas (**India Census, 2011**). Rural development involves development of various essential necessities required by the rural in their day to day life such as employment, housing, roads and other infrastructures and agriculture of food crops and nonfood crops. The rural development also implies to drinking water and sanitation management, forest resources management, watershed, dry land and drought management and rural industrialization., which has broader but specific than to agricultural development. It is broader because it is much broader than agricultural development. Rural development include attention to all aspects of economies which include agriculture, natural resources, non-farm sector, rural infrastructure, education and health aiming sustainable development for enhanced rural livelihood

The Rural development programmes have commenced in India in 1952, for over past 65 years these programmes have been implemented through all state Governments. Hence as per the scheduled programmes under Ministry of Rural development and Ministry of Drinking Water and sanitation, various rural development programmes are being conducted all over India since long.

Government of Kerala promulgate various rural development programs through Commissionerate of rural development, by unifying both central and state proposed schemes since 1987 these programmes are being implemented under different names with due modifications which are specific to the social, cultural, geographical and demographical needs. (**Commissionerate of Rural Development, 2015**)

As the successful implementation of the programmes demands thorough knowledge on the subjects, the department also impart training to its stake holders namely Government officials and Elected Panchayati Raj Institution (PRI) Members during their term in the office. These training imparted by Ministry of Rural development and Ministry of Drinking Water and sanitation through Commissionerate of rural development, Kerala, are broadly categorized into Schemes for generation of wage employment, Schemes for generation of self-employment, Schemes for Provision of housing to rural poor, Schemes for Construction of all-weather rural roads and Schemes for Watershed Development and Schemes for Sanitation (**Ministry of Rural development, n.d**). These programmes are Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment

Guarantee Act (**MGNREGA**) , Integrated Watershed Management Programme(**IWMP**), The Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (**PMGSY**), Swarnajayanti Gram Swarajgar Yojana (**SGSY**),Swachh Bharat Abhiyan(**SBA**),Rural Infrastructure Development Fund (**RIDF**) , Sustainable Income Generation for Self Help Groups (**SI for SHG**),Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan (**NBA**) ,Indira Awas Yojana (**IAY**) and Total Sanitation Campaign (**TSC**) are the prominent schemes prevailing in Kerala during the study period.

These programmes are implemented through Gram Panchayat Offices, Block Panchayat Offices, District Rural Development Agencies (DRDAs). Further to implement these programmes, training on some of these schemes are imparted through State Institute of Rural Development, (S.I.R.D), Extension Training Centre (ETC), Block Panchayat Offices and, Gram Panchayat offices to Government officials,elected public representatives and General public. (**Ministry of Rural Development 2015**).

This study is focused on the Positive aspects Rural Development Training conducted in Kannur District of Kerala. The study was conducted on the Elected Panchayati Raj Institution (PRI) Members who held the office during 2010 to 2015 and thus feedback is taken in 2016 to 2017. The programmes selected for the study are important programmes namely MGNREGA, IAY, IWMP, TSC and PMGSY .As the study pertain to Kannur district, it involves all PRIs of District Panchayat, 11 Block Panchayats and 81 Gram Panchayats of Kannur districts.

Rural Development Programmes

Five prominent programmes **MGNREGA, IAY, IWMP, TSC** and **PMGSY** are taken for this study and are explained below.

The schemes under Commissionerate of rural development, Government of Kerala are as follows:

Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) is a social security measure promulgated by Government of India in the form of labor law which guarantee the right to work. It guarantees 100 days of wage employment in a financial year to every household whose adult members volunteer to do unskilled manual work so that livelihood security in rural areas are ensured.

Indira Awas Yojana (IAY) is meant for BPL families who are either houseless or having inadequate housing facilities for constructing a safe and durable shelter. The constitution of India places rural housing under the purview of State government and Panchayat Raj Institutions. The Scheme comes under the concept of Shelter for all, in purview that rural housing is the major anti-poverty measures for marginalised rural population

Integrated Watershed Management Programme (IWMP) are meant to restore the ecological balance of the soil, vegetative cover and water by harnessing, conserving and developing

degraded natural resources . This programmes thereby enables multi-cropping and the introduction of diverse agro-based activities which help to provide sustainable livelihoods.

The Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (PMGSY) is a nationwide plan in India to connect all unconnected villages by providing all-weather roads. It was launched to provide connectivity to unconnected habitations as part of a poverty reduction strategy. Government of India has set high level and uniform technical and management standard and developed policy and planning at each state level for the construction and management of rural road networks.

Total Sanitation Campaign (TSC): In India too like other countries, contaminated food and water have been the main sources of many health problems. Duly understanding the importance of safe drinking water, Government of India which started Central Rural sanitation programme (CRSP) in 1986 in its concept of sanitation had included personal hygiene, home sanitation, safe water, garbage disposal, excreta disposal and waste water disposal. With this broader concept of sanitation, CRSP adopted a new approach with the name "Total sanitation Campaign (TSC), with effect from 1999. TSC is meant for total sanitation of villages through the solid and liquid waste disposal and intensive campaign for awareness generation and health education to create a felt need for personal, household and environmental sanitation facilities.

Rural Development Training

Training is purely vocational. It involves improving aptitudes, skills and abilities to perform a specific job. Education is person oriented and training is job-oriented (**Reddy , 2013**) the purpose of training here is to enable the beneficiaries with basic knowledge and skills to effectively use the Rural development programs. While the basic concepts of training is to transfer of knowledge and skill, it is anticipated that beneficiaries' attitude also changes with it.

Under the Rural Development Commissionerate , the Training is imparted through Gram Panchayat levels , Block Panchayat levels , District Rural Development Agencies (DRDAs) , Extension Training Centres (ETCs) at Kottarakkara, Mannuthy and Taliparamba and State Institute of Rural Development (SIRD) Kottarakkara to officials below the rank of Block Development Officers (BDOs) as well as elected representatives of Panchayat Raj Institutions. In addition Training is imparted through National Institute of Rural Development, Hyderabad which is the National nodal agency of the Rural development Training.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Hawkins (1994) said that learning to be viewed as more multi-faceted and dynamic process which causes a change at the heart of the learner. Further as learning aids in creating culture and developing the knowledge, organizations and individuals alike must become continuous learners.

According to **Mawer (1996)** Trainees' credibility is a significant factor in training. The trainees' aptitude, skill, knowledge, past experience and attitude towards the subject and training matters.

According to **Quinones and Ehrenstein (1997)**, Training is a systematic process whereby the trainees are provided with knowledge, skills and develop positive behavioral attitudes. Organizations all over the world are spending lot of money, time and other scarce resources for training. Training will enhance abilities and characteristics that enable a job holder to accomplish the activities described in a task statement

Kirkpatrick, (1998) while explaining four evaluation model,described that the effectiveness of the training is to be assessed not only at the end of the training period, but also on the job in practical field. As this practice is rarely done in many organizations, it is to be done by appropriate training evaluation models.

Elmishri (2000) agrees that the need for training may result from drives to improve quality, reduce waste, redesign jobs, and make changes in the work process or materials. A well-defined Training objective and a well-structured evaluation system of knowledge, skill and behavior will enable to the measure of success of training programme.

According to **Aswathappa (2000)**, the term training involve the process of increasing the aptitudes, skills, Knowledge abilities of the employees to perform specific jobs. Training helps in updating old talents and developing new ones.

Jackson and Schuler (2000) refers that training as the act of improving competencies needed today or in the future., while development refers to improving competencies over the long term

Duch et al,(2001) explained the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) is a teaching method in which complex real-world problems are used as the vehicle to promote student learning of concepts and principles as opposed to direct presentation of facts and concepts. In addition to course content, PBL can promote the development of critical thinking skills, problem-solving abilities, and communication skills. It can also provide opportunities for working in groups, finding and evaluating research materials, and life-long learning.

Burke et al (2006) and **Colquitt et al (2000)** had shown that general mental ability has strong relationship than personality factor for effective training. Thus good mental ability will yield positive output of the training.

Bates and Davis (2010) while describing the application bridge model, had described that there is a need to create opportunity to transfer learning by demonstrating the trainees how to apply the newly acquired knowledge at workplace. They stressed that trainee is able to practice the theoretical aspects learned in training programme in actual work environment. It is stated that training efforts must be rigorous and continuous.

Subramanian et al (2012) described that, **the** effort to use training as a tool to help balance an organization in a dynamic environment must be continuous. There must be constant matching of individual and organizational needs in a system which is biased towards neither.

According to **Lindsay et al (2012)**, policy makers in Scotland, the other British nations and across the industrialized world have sought to increase participation in work-related training as a route to improved competitiveness. The study had shown that in terms of the factors associated with participation in work-related training, remarkable similarities across the public and private sectors, though the proportion of public sector employees receiving training is higher than that in the private sector. The studies further indicated that, trade union presence in the workplace also had powerful positive effects on training participation. The study indicates that work related training is appreciated by both participants and organizers all over the world and is considered as positiveness of the training.

According to **Hamza (2012)** .the capacity and commitment are to be considered while imparting the training .As each course demands certain expertise, skill and knowledge the capacity, qualification and past experience are essentially to be accounted to obtain positive outcome of training.

As stated by **Falola et al (2014)** , if there is any gap between the existing and desired Knowledge, Skill and Attitude (KSA) . For enhancing the growth of KSA and for ultimate improvement in the performance of the trainees, training is mandatory

According to **Gane (2017)** in training, a homogeneous group is most desirable. The difference in group will lead to widen the learning pace between slower learner and faster learner. As the course duration increases the gap further widens. Hence homogeneous group among trainees ensure the positive ness of the training.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Rural Development training was chosen as it was felt that as this field would support the study for typicality. The study is concerned with the Positive aspect of training. Since 1952 Government of India had promulgated numerous rural development programme. . Many of them completed their tenure and most of them were transformed to some other programmes. According to **Ashley and Maxwell, (2001)** , rural aspects are changing with demography, economy, social changes and rural and agricultural environments. Further as per**Murdoch, (2000)**, the rural development involves a new paradigm involving new theories of innovation and learning.**Sharma and Malhotra, (1977)**.Stated that under these circumstances there is a need to bring entire rural population under the main stream of activity. Hence it is felt that in order to ascertain a fruitful rural development, the training to be imparted, where the positive aspects are taken care for its full effectiveness

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To assess the positive aspect of the Rural development training imparted to elected members of Panchayati Raj Institutions in Kannur district
2. To assess the percent of participation of five important programmes namely MGNREGA, IAY, IWMP , TSC and PMGSY during the study period

METHODOLOGY OF STUDY

Research Design

The research involves both primary data as well as secondary data analysis . Primary data involves structured questionnaire which consists of the introduction, questions pertaining to the programme the respondent attended and 10 criteria. Five prominent programmes MGNREGA, IAY, IWMP, TSC and PMGSY are taken for this study. The responses were to be marked on Likert scale for the 10 criteria. The questionnaires were distributed by post and received back by hand. The secondary data are obtained through literature obtained through various printed sources like journals, books, conference proceedings, reports and Government orders.

Universe

- The universe of the study consists of elected members of Panchayati Raj Institutions in Kannur district

Sampling technique

- Cent percent samples have been taken to study the responses of elected members of Panchayati Raj Institutions in Kannur District Panchayat and all 11 Block Panchayats. Only two members namely Gram Panchayat President and Vice Presidents are taken as samples from 81 gram Panchayats, as they get better opportunities to attend the training programmes and generally they possess better knowledge on the subjects than other members. Hence Judgment sampling is done in this case.

Sample Size

- 315 members only responded back to questionnaire and is thus considered as sample size for the study.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The respondents were to answer pertaining to the training they had undergone during their tenure of full five years in office from FY 2010 -11 to FY 2015-16. As per Kirkpatrick's four level evaluation (**Kirkpatrick , 1998**) and CIRO model training evaluation (**Warr et al , 1970**), the result or outcome of training need to be taken only after certain time gap from the end of training, normally about an year . To facilitate this , the data for the study is collected in 2017.

DISCUSSION AND RESULT

The study is conducted on five important programmes namely MGNREGA, IAY, IWMP, TSC and PMGSY during the study period. As seen in the Table No.1, it is seen that all programmes are not attended by all 315 respondents. The percentage of participation is shown in Fig No.1.

Table No.1 - Percent of Participation for each programme.

Program	No of Participations	Percent of Respondents
MGNREGA	241	34.48
IAY	115	16.45
IWMP	139	19.89
TSC	103	14.73
PMGSY	101	14.45
Total	699	100.00

Fig No. 1 – Percent of Participation for each programme

The study shows that highest participation in MGNREGA at 34.48 percent and lowest participation is in PMGSY at 14.45 percent...

The analysis based on ten Criteria of Positive Aspects of the training and responses obtained in respect of all five important programmes is appended below. The responses are obtained on Likert scaling for 1 strongly disagreed, 2 disagreed, 3 Neutral, 4 agreed and 5 strongly agreed..

Table 2 Criteria 1 - Training pertain to specific areas of work

Program	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
MGNREGA	241	2.70	1.72
IAY	115	2.99	1.69
IWMP	139	3.00	1.69
TSC	103	2.89	1.74
PMGSY	101	3.45	1.60

The responses towards the criteria “Training pertain to specific areas of work” pertaining to the five training programmes as per Table No. 2 indicates that mean ± standard deviation of

responses pertaining to training of MGNREA is 2.70 ± 1.72 , IAY is 2.99 ± 1.69 , IWMP is 3.00 ± 1.69 , TSC is 2.89 ± 1.74 and PMGSY is 3.45 ± 1.60 respectively .Thus test shows that as per Likert scale criteria , MGNREA is in disagreement level , IAY is in disagreement level, IWMP is in neutral level, TSC is in disagreement level and PMGSY is in agreement level . The result shows that the responses towards the subject criteria is highest on training pertaining to PMGSY and lowest in respect of MGNREGA.

Table No. 3Criteria 2 - Training takes into account interest and mental capabilities of trainees

Program	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
MGNREGA	241	2.56	1.71
IAY	115	2.70	1.65
IWMP	139	3.24	1.62
TSC	103	2.83	1.79
PMGSY	101	2.54	1.70

The responses towards the criteria “Training takes into account interest and mental capabilities of trainees” pertaining to the five training programmes as per Table No. 3 indicates that mean \pm standard deviation of responses pertaining to training of MGNREA is 2.56 ± 1.71 , IAY is 2.70 ± 1.65 , IWMP is 3.24 ± 1.62 , TSC is 2.83 ± 1.79 and PMGSY is 2.54 ± 1.70 respectively .Thus test shows that as per Likert scale criteria , MGNREA is in disagreement level , IAY is in disagreement level, IWMP is in agreement level, TSC is in disagreement level and PMGSY is in disagreement level . The result shows that the responses towards the subject criteria is highest on training pertaining to IWMP and lowest in respect of PMGSY.

Table No.4Criteria 3 - Tools and Techniques shown in training often exist in the work environment

Program	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
MGNREGA	241	1.95	1.57
IAY	115	2.55	1.70
IWMP	139	2.88	1.72
TSC	103	2.93	1.83
PMGSY	101	2.68	1.61

The responses towards the criteria “Tools and Techniques shown in Training often exist in the Work environment” pertaining to the five training programmes as per Table No. 3 indicates that mean \pm standard deviation of responses pertaining to training of MGNREA is 1.95 ± 1.57 , IAY is 2.55 ± 1.70 , IWMP is 2.88 ± 1.72 , TSC is 2.93 ± 1.83 and PMGSY is 2.68 ± 1.61 respectively

.Thus test shows that as per Likert scale criteria , MGNREA is in strongly disagreement level and IAY, IWMP, TSC and PMGSY are in disagreement level . The result shows that the responses towards the subject criteria is highest on training pertaining to TSC and lowest in respect of MGNREGA

Fig No. 5. Criteria 4 - Training programs covers issues and solution to problems that may arise in the field

Program	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
MGNREGA	241	1.80	1.48
IAY	115	2.53	1.68
IWMP	139	2.25	1.55
TSC	103	3.18	1.80
PMGSY	101	2.93	1.72

The responses towards the criteria "Training programs covers issues and solution to problems that may arise in the field " pertaining to the five training programmes as per Table No. 4 indicates that mean \pm standard deviation of responses pertaining to training of MGNREA is 1.80 ± 1.48 , IAY is 2.53 ± 1.68 , IWMP is 2.25 ± 1.55 , TSC is 3.18 ± 1.80 and PMGSY is 2.93 ± 1.72 respectively .Thus test shows that as per Likert scale criteria , MGNREA is in strongly disagreement level , IAY is in disagreement level, IWMP is in disagreement level, TSC is in agreement level and PMGSY is disagreement level . The result shows that the responses towards the subject criteria is highest on training pertaining to TSC and lowest in respect of MGNREGA.

Table No. 6: Criteria 5 - Training is often take into account the qualification and past experience of trainees.

Program	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
MGNREGA	241	2.18	1.70
IAY	115	2.54	1.70
IWMP	139	2.22	1.58
TSC	103	2.38	1.80
PMGSY	101	2.66	1.67

The responses towards the criteria "Training is often take into account the qualification and past experience of trainees"" pertaining to the five training programmes as per Table No. 5 indicates that mean \pm standard deviation of responses pertaining to training of MGNREA is 2.18 ± 1.70 , IAY is 2.54 ± 1.70 , IWMP is 2.22 ± 1.58 , TSC is 2.38 ± 1.80 and PMGSY is 2.66 ± 1.67 respectively .Thus test shows that as per Likert scale criteria , all programmes MGNREA, IAY, IWMP, TSC and PMGSY are in disagreement level . The result shows that the responses towards the subject criteria is only marginally different and highest is on training pertaining to PMGSY and lowest in respect of MGNREGA.

Table No.7 Criteria 6 - The trainees are selected for training based on credibility

Program	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
MGNREGA	241	2.13	1.65
IAY	115	2.19	1.75
IWMP	139	2.40	1.64
TSC	103	2.33	1.76
PMGSY	101	2.78	1.70

The responses towards the criteria “The trainees are selected for training based on credibility” pertaining to the five training programmes as per Table No. 6 indicates that mean \pm standard deviation of responses pertaining to training of MGNREA is 2.13 ± 1.65 , IAY is 2.19 ± 1.75 , IWMP is 2.40 ± 1.64 , TSC is 2.33 ± 1.76 and PMGSY is 2.78 ± 1.70 respectively. Thus test shows that as per Likert scale criteria, all programmes MGNREA, IAY, IWMP, TSC and PMGSY are in disagreement level. The result shows that the responses towards the subject criteria only is marginally different and highest is on training pertaining to PMGSY and lowest in respect of MGNREGA.

Table No.8 Criteria 7 - The training is normally meant for homogenous groups

Program	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
MGNREGA	241	1.92	1.59
IAY	115	2.82	1.72
IWMP	139	2.45	1.66
TSC	103	2.47	1.84
PMGSY	101	2.58	1.58

The responses towards the criteria “The training is normally meant for homogenous groups” pertaining to the five training programmes as per Table No. 7 indicates that mean \pm standard deviation of responses pertaining to training of MGNREA is 1.92 ± 1.59 , IAY is 2.82 ± 1.72 , IWMP is 2.45 ± 1.66 , TSC is 2.47 ± 1.84 and PMGSY is 2.58 ± 1.58 respectively. Thus test shows that as per Likert scale criteria, MGNREA is in strongly disagreement level and IAY, IWMP, TSC and PMGSY are in disagreement level. The result shows that the responses towards the subject criteria is highest on training pertaining to IAY and lowest in respect of MGNREGA.

Table No. 9: Criteria 8- The training is often Problem based

Program	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
MGNREGA	241	2.10	1.70
IAY	115	2.08	1.58
IWMP	139	3.20	1.67
TSC	103	3.23	1.86
PMGSY	101	2.68	1.73

The responses towards the criteria “The training is often problem based” pertaining to the five training programmes as per Table No. 8 indicates that mean \pm standard deviation of responses pertaining to training of MGNREA is 2.10 ± 1.70 , IAY is 2.08 ± 1.58 , IWMP is 3.20 ± 1.67 , TSC is 3.23 ± 1.86 and PMGSY is 2.68 ± 1.73 respectively. Thus test shows that as per Likert scale criteria, MGNREA, IAY and PMGSY are in disagreement level and IWMP and TSC are in agreement level. The result shows that the responses towards the subject criteria is highest on training pertaining to TSC and lowest in respect of IAY.

Table No. 10Criteria 9 - There is often based on specific trainees expectations after the training

Program	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
MGNREGA	241	1.98	1.59
IAY	115	2.36	1.55
IWMP	139	2.34	1.68
TSC	103	2.84	1.86
PMGSY	101	2.32	1.52

The responses towards the criteria “There is often based on specific expectations from trainees after the training” pertaining to the five training programmes as per Table No. 9 indicates that mean \pm standard deviation of responses regarding the training of MGNREA is 1.98 ± 1.59 , IAY is 2.36 ± 1.55 , IWMP is 2.34 ± 1.68 , TSC is 2.84 ± 1.86 and PMGSY is 2.32 ± 1.52 respectively. Thus test shows that as per Likert scale criteria, MGNREA is in strongly disagreement level and IAY, IWMP, TSC and PMGSY are in disagreement level. The result shows that the responses towards the subject criteria is highest on training pertaining to TSC and lowest in respect of MGNREGA

Table No.11Criteria 10 - Training has additional facilities to those who want to develop their skills and capabilities.

Program	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
MGNREGA	241	2.11	1.60
IAY	115	2.33	1.75
IWMP	139	2.51	1.70
TSC	103	2.42	1.80
PMGSY	101	2.34	1.57

The responses towards the criteria “Training has additional facilities to those who want to develop their skills and capabilities” pertaining to the five training programmes as per Table No. 10 indicates that mean \pm standard deviation of responses regarding training of MGNREA is 2.11 ± 1.60 , IAY is 2.33 ± 1.75 , IWMP is 2.51 ± 1.70 , TSC is 2.42 ± 1.80 and PMGSY is 2.34 ± 1.57 respectively .Thus test shows that as per Likert scale criteria , all programmes MGNREA, IAY, IWMP, TSC and PMGSY are in disagreement level . The result shows that the responses towards the subject criteria is highest on training pertaining to IWMP and lowest in respect of MGNREGA.

Table No.12 - Overall Criteria about Positive Aspects

Program	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
MGNREGA	241	2.14	1.03
IAY	115	2.51	.92
IWMP	139	2.65	.80
TSC	103	2.75	.95
PMGSY	101	2.70	.92

The responses towards overall positiveness by all ten criteria , pertaining to the five training programmes as per Table No. 12 indicates that mean \pm standard deviation of responses pertaining to training of MGNREA is 2.14 ± 1.03 , IAY is 2.51 ± 0.92 , IWMP is 2.65 ± 0.80 , TSC is 2.75 ± 0.95 and PMGSY is 2.70 ± 0.92 respectively .Thus test shows that as per Likert scale criteria , all programmes MGNREA, IAY, IWMP, TSC and PMGSY are in disagreement level .The result shows that the responses towards the subject criteria is highest on training pertaining to TSC and lowest in respect of MGNREGA.

1. FINDINGS

The study found that,

- a) All the respondents did not attend all the training programmes. The study shows that highest participation is in MGNREGA at 34.48 percent and lowest participation is in PMGSY at 14.45 percent.
- b) Criteria 1 ,Training pertain to specific areas of work, is found highest on training pertaining to PMGSY and lowest in respect of MGNREGA .
- c) Criteria2, Training takes into account interest and mental capabilities of trainees, is found highest on training pertaining to IWMP and lowest in respect of PMGSY
- d) Criteria3, Tools and Techniques shown in Training often exist in the Work environment, is found highest on training pertaining to TSC and lowest in respect of MGNREGA.

- e) Criteria 4, Training programs covers issues and solution to problems that may arise in the field, is found highest on training pertaining to TSC and lowest in respect of MGNREGA.
- f) Criteria 5, Training often take into account the qualification and past experience of trainees, is found highest on training pertaining to PMGSY and lowest in respect of MGNREGA
- g) Criteria 6, Trainees are selected for training based on credibility , is found highest on training pertaining to PMGSY and lowest in respect of MGNREGA
- h) Criteria 7, Training is normally meant for homogenous groups is found highest on training pertaining to IAY and lowest in respect of MGNREGA.
- i) Criteria 8, Training is often issue based, is found highest on training pertaining to TSC and lowest in respect of IAY.
- j) Criteria 9, Training is often based on specific expectations from trainees after the training, is found highest on training pertaining to TSC and lowest in respect of MGNREGA.
- k) Criteria 10, Training has additional facilities to those who want to develop their skills and capabilities, is found highest on training pertaining to IWMP and lowest in respect of MGNREGA.
- l) The overall responses by all ten criteria towards positive aspects indicates that the highest response is obtained with regard to training pertaining to TSC and lowest in respect of MGNREGA.
- m) It is thus found that though MGNREGA had highest participation of 34.48 percent in comparison to other programmes and in all eight out of ten criteria as shown above, this programme had lowest positive aspects.

2. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the study it is seen that TSC followed by PMGSY has shown highest positive aspects in training. MGNREGA though highly participated by more than one third of participants at 34.48 percent and eight out of ten criteria had shown lowest positive aspects in training. Therefore, there is an urgent need to modify the MGNREGA training which will enhance its positive aspects.

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